

NEUROPEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING OF TEACHER AND STUDENT

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A dynamic model of the development of critical thinking of subjects of the educational process at a university in various implementations makes it possible to solve a number of problems that have both theoretical and practical significance [1]. These are: building individual (subjectively optimal) trajectories for the development of critical thinking of teachers and students; identifying criteria and indicators of the effectiveness of the implementation of these trajectories, defining and analyzing neuropedagogical conditions for the development of critical thinking.

When identifying neuropedagogical conditions for the development of critical thinking of teachers and students, it is necessary to take into account the following points:

- individual typological characteristics of a university teacher [2],
- problem areas for the development of critical thinking among technical students and students of humanities [3; 4],
- basic principles of neuropedagogy.

Moreover, it should be remembered that a condition is “not only something that affects a thing, but also something without which a thing as such cannot exist, which serves as a prerequisite, the basis for its occurrence” [2], it is a set of circumstances aimed at creating an environment for implementing the process of developing critical thinking of subjects of the educational process at a university and ensuring its existence and effective functioning. Let us consider in detail the neuropedagogical conditions we have identified.

Awareness by the teacher and student of the need to take into account the data of neuropedagogical diagnostics (self-diagnosis). The identification of this condition is due to the fact that the effective development of critical thinking of both the teacher and the student is possible only taking into account their psychodynamic

characteristics, knowledge of which allows one to predict the behavior of an individual in difficult situations of stress and monotony and helps in adapting to changing conditions of the university environment. A person's understanding of his individual psychological differences allows him to effectively use his own potential to achieve maximum effect in the development of critical thinking and its use in professional activities.

To implement this condition, teachers and students must master methods for assessing the following individual parameters: neurodynamic properties (activity and reactivity, rigidity and plasticity, extroversion and introversion, emotional excitability, anxiety), temperament, developmental characteristics higher mental functions (memory, perception, speech), the predominant style of thinking, individual style of activity, features of self-regulation (active or passive style) [3].

It should be noted that the activity of a higher school teacher (a student's educational activity) can either contribute to the realization of his individual capabilities or contradict them. The development of critical thinking, aimed at a more complete use by the teacher and student of the diagnosed potential capabilities, self-regulation skills and improvement of individual qualities, acts as an essential aspect of developing the professional suitability of subjects of the educational process at a university.

Based on the general algorithm for the development of critical thinking of a teacher developed in the study, which is based on reflective self-analysis of individual characteristics and experience of self-regulatory development of this type of thinking, we asked university teachers to determine their inherent type of temperament and the predominant type thinking (left hemisphere or right hemisphere). Unfortunately, many teachers (32%) did not answer this question, without defining, even on an intuitive level, their style of thinking and without remembering the classical types of temperament. As a result of the research, it was found that both teachers and students are very poorly versed in the individual psychological characteristics of their own personality and do not know the methods of neurodiagnostics of personality traits according to various parameters.

We can identify the most typical styles of teacher activity in the context of the problem under consideration:

1 – individual style of activity, not focused either on high results or on concern for the development of critical thinking of the student as an individual and personality; The educational process for a teacher is only a means of self-affirmation (often at the expense of others) and false self-realization;

2 – individual style of activity, in which there is an excessive focus on the unconscious desires of students, little attention is paid to the final result in the form of the necessary level of critical thinking. For example, taking into account the students' inclination towards traditional convergent thinking, the desire to work in monologue mode rather than co-creation and co-management, which clearly does not contribute to the development of the basic characteristics of critical thinking[15]. In addition, the role of the personality of the teacher himself, who dissolves in the student mass, is leveled out;

3 – individual style of activity, result-oriented – a high level of development of critical thinking, but does not involve work on developing the individuality of students; Teachers often work mechanically: responsibly, but “without a soul.” This may be due to the insufficient psychological or pedagogical preparedness of teachers, their ignorance of the characteristics of student age, the discrepancy between the required developmental teaching technologies and the individual characteristics of teachers and students;

4 – individual style of activity, aimed at good interaction and mutual understanding between the teacher and students, but with an unknown or misunderstood pedagogical reality. As a result, as a rule, the educational function of the educational process is not sufficiently implemented, which results in a low level of education and development of critical thinking of students;

5 – the teacher, having certain professional knowledge and skills (as a rule, this is a good command of the educational material), is focused on his goals of the educational process, but considers them one-sidedly, ignoring the different styles of students processing the information received (at present The university is responsible not for the development of students' abilities, but for the volume and content of knowledge that is not directly included in the development fund). At the same time, it is possible that there is a difference in the value orientations of teachers and students, as well as their emotional incompatibility, differences in thinking styles, and cognitive dissonance.

According to A.V. Libin, teachers with a pronounced emotional orientation towards themselves are characterized by anxiety and a tendency to depression [5]. Teachers who are prone to an impulsive style of behavior, accompanied by high levels of emotionality, develop a compensatory mechanism that restrains possible significant energy costs (due to a low level of self-regulation) in the case of negative external reinforcement. The development of critical thinking of subjects of the educational process is influenced by the relationship between the emotional and intellectual components, expressed in the unity of their mental development and

emotional preferences in relation to a particular cognitive style and emotional satisfaction from its use.

Critical analysis by teachers and students of their activities, their awareness of existing shortcomings naturally evokes negative emotions. It should be noted that teachers, like students, to a greater extent than themselves, attribute emotionality and subjectivity to colleagues and classmates, considering them biased in relation to adherence to a certain system of mental actions.

In this regard, we can formulate the following condition necessary for the effective development of critical thinking of a teacher and student: activation of the individual creative potential of subjects of the educational process by increasing the share of creative forms and methods of teaching and learning as an important factor in the development of decision skills non-standard professionally oriented situations and searching for alternative ways to solve them.

Testing reasonable neuropedagogical conditions is possible with the implementation of cognitive technologies for teaching teachers and students to effectively develop individual trajectories for the development of critical thinking.

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